

The Push, Pull, and Moorings Factors on Customer's Switching Intention of an Indonesian Fashion Brand

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Abstract:- Fashion was one of the important industries in the world that made a significant contribution to the global economy, including here in Indonesia. The fashion industry was a dynamic business with uncertain demand caused by the variety of styles and consumer preferences. Retail fashion was a series of business activities that added value to products and services sold to customers for personal or family purposes. Robinson (Ramayana) was one of the major retailers with a total of 119 stores spread across various regions in Indonesia. Since 2016, there had been a decrease in consumer spending that continued until 2017 due to economic sluggishness. The Indonesian economy improved in 2017 with a growth rate of 5.1 percent due to increased investment and exports, but it still did not have an impact on the return of consumer spending. This was influenced by significant electricity tariffs that offset the impact of the growing income of the lower-middle consumer segment. Recognizing the importance of consumers role in business operations and maintaining long-term relationships with customers, companies in today market dynamics were becoming more customer oriented. It was important for companies to evaluate their own service quality while studying consumer behavior and factors that could influence customers to switch. This research applied the Push, Pull, and Mooring Factors methods, which examined the significant influence of push, pull, and mooring factors on customers' desire to switch.

Keywords:- Fashion; customers; push factors; pull factors; mooring factors; desire to switch.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fashion was one of the important industries in the world that made a significant contribution to the global economy. According to Euromonitor International's report, in 2014, the clothing and footwear market reached a value of 1.7 trillion US dollars, and it was projected to grow to 2.2 trillion US dollars by 2019. This led many countries, including Indonesia, to strive for advancement in the fashion industry. The fashion industry was a dynamic business with uncertain demand caused by the variety of styles and consumer preferences. [1.] stated that the fashion industry had a wide and hierarchical scope ranging from excellence (haute couture), quality (ready-to-wear), to snobbery (mass production). Fashion as a clothing industry started to emerge towards the end of the 19th century with the establishment of the House of Worth by Charles Frederick Worth in Paris in 1858. This paved the way for the development of ready-to-wear clothing, which allowed

fashion consumption to expand widely. The trend of designers creating ready-to-wear garments gained strength in the 1920s after Coco Chanel, Lucien Lelong, and Jean Patou officially sold their ready-to-wear collections in their couture houses. Following its evolution, today the global fashion industry is dominated by ready-to-wear and mass production businesses. Due to the increasing influence of fashion needs, advancing technology, economic growth, improved quality of life for the middle and upper-middle class, and higher per capita income, the retail sector in the fashion industry has experienced significant growth. According to [2.], retail refers to a sequence of commercial endeavors aimed at enhancing the worth of products and services offered to individuals or families for personal use or household purposes. Supported by the growing economy of the middle class and increasing per capita income, retail has flourished in Indonesia. Data from the Semarang Population and Civil Registration Office in 2016 recorded that Semarang, the capital of Central Java, had a population of 1,694,412 people spread across various areas. Currently, there are about 27 modern shopping centers in Semarang.

Robinson Department Store (previously known as Ramayana) was one of the major retailers with a total of 119 stores spread across various regions in Indonesia. The philosophy behind PT Ramayana Lestari Sentosa Tbk., which began in 1978 and has been consistently followed for the past four decades, can be summarized as 'value for money.' Its goal was to serve the lower to lower-middle-class consumers, characterized by relatively minimal income, with durable, attractive, and, most importantly, affordable garment and household products. Robinson first went public in July 1996. Currently, there are 7,096 billion shares in circulation, with a market capitalization of Rp 8.48 trillion, equivalent to USD 628.0 million. Robinson's vision is to be a 'solution for fashion products,' with a mission to provide a unique, attractive, and entertaining shopping experience. With forty years of experience in the business, Robinson offers high-quality Indonesian products, such as clothing, food, and household necessities, to three generations of Indonesian consumers. Robinson offers a range of products, including clothing, shoes, bags, toys, stationery, household items, and supermarkets. Since 2016, there has been a decline in consumer spending that continued until 2017 due to the sluggish economy. The Indonesian economy improved in 2017 with a growth rate of 5.1% due to increased investment and exports, but it still did not have an impact on the return of consumer spending. This was influenced by significant electricity tariffs that offset the impact of the rapid growth of income in the lower-middle consumer segment. Several foreign retailers, including some department stores, chose to close their

operations amidst signs that consumers in Indonesia would increasingly shop online. In an effort to address this background, Matahari, one of Robinson's competitors, managed to achieve a 1.2% year-on-year increase in product sales to Rp 17,496.3 billion, while Robinson's financial report as of March 31, 2018, showed a decline compared to the previous year.

Robinson had a mission as a leading retailer in Indonesia, with smart cost control, market adaptation, improved customer service, and maintaining mutually beneficial relationships with business partners to enhance efficiency and shareholder value. With the shadow of inflation and income pressures, Robinson aimed to increase profit margins and compete with other leading retailers. In terms of brand value, Robinson still tended to lag behind its biggest competitor, Matahari. According to [3.], this was influenced by the store image and store atmosphere of the respective retailers. [3.] stated that a case study at Robinson Department Store in Mal Ciputra Semarang showed poor product quality, limited product variety, unappealing store decorations, and unattractive product displays as some reasons that did not support customer repeat purchases at the department store. In addition to the aforementioned factors, the quality of retail services can also influence consumer behavior. Poor service quality from service providers can lead to customer complaints and deter consumers from making repeat transactions at the retail store. According to [4.], consumers can express complaints and dissatisfaction with service through negative word-of-mouth, aggression/attacks, and ultimately switch to other competitors.

Researchers [5.] conducted a study on customer switching behavior, which resulted in the Push-Pull-Mooring model to illustrate the phenomenon of customer switching. Push factors encompass negative aspects related to the existing service provider, compelling customers to switch. These factors comprise elements such as low quality, low satisfaction, low value, low trust, low commitment, and a perception of high prices. On the other hand, pull factors encompass positive attributes offered by alternative service providers or competitors, attracting customers towards switching. Alternative attractiveness, which represents customers' expectations of better service from the new service provider compared to the previous one, is included in the pull factors. Mooring factors are factors that can hinder or support customer switching from the old service provider to the new service provider. Mooring factors consist of customer attitudes towards switching, subjective norms or social influences, switching costs, past behavior, and the tendency to seek variety.

This research aims to examine the push factors, pull factors, and mooring factors of Robinson's customers, as well as their intention to switch to this fashion brand. Hopefully, the results will help stakeholders make decisions

regarding the fashion brand based on the behavior of Indonesian customers captured in this research.

II. LITERATURES REVIEW

A. *Switching Brand*

The term "brand" originated from the old word "brandr," which means "to brand," referring to the activity frequently performed by American cattle farmers of marking their livestock to facilitate ownership identification before selling them in the market [6.]. According to [7.], a brand should not be seen merely as a brand but should be recognized as a living entity. Based on this statement, he suggests that a brand should be regarded not as a fixed product or service but as an organization, person, or symbol that sets it apart from other brands. The behavior of brand switching among customers is a complex phenomenon influenced by behavioral factors, competition, and time [7.]. According to [9.], brand switching by consumers is caused by the search for variety. On the other hand, brand switching can be also occurring in products with low involvement purchasing characteristics.

B. *Push, Pull, Mooring Factors*

Push-pull is a component of the Push-Pull-Mooring (PPM) migration model with a long history, dating back to the 19th century. [5.] model of PPM as figured in Fig. 1 was applied in this research. [10.] defines push factors as factors that motivate customers to switch from their existing service provider, assuming they have a negative influence on quality of life indicators. Within the realm of services, these push factors are often linked to inadequate service quality delivered by the provider, motivating customers to transition to an alternative service provider. Factors such as quality, satisfaction, value, trust, commitment, and price perception can act as drivers for customer switching. On the other hand, pull factors are positive factors present in alternative service providers that can attract customers to switch [5.]. One reason why consumer consider switching to substitute products is that substitute products have more advantages compared to the original products. According to the push-pull paradigm, the positive factors associated with alternative service providers will attract customers to switch. The variable representing these pull factors is alternative attractiveness, which refers to the positive characteristics of the alternative service provider that positively influence customers' switching intentions. [5.] states that the push-pull paradigm is not sufficient to capture the complexity of migration decisions. The push-pull paradigm becomes more complex with the presence of intervening variables. Barriers such as family obligations and high switching costs can impede migration. Therefore, even with strong push and pull factors, a person may not necessarily migrate. The inhibiting variables include attitudes towards switching, subjective norms (social influence), switching costs, past behavior, and the inclination to seek variety.

Fig. 1: PPM model by [5.] applied in this research

III. RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, the significance of the push, pull, and mooring factors was measured. The variables involved in this study can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Variables Involved in This Research

Variables	Indicators	Code	Source
Service Quality	Overall, I considered Robinson retail to be good.	SQ1	[5.]
	Generally, the quality of Robinson’s products is good.	SQ2	[5.]
	The employees at Robinson did not provide good responses when I was shopping.	SQ3	[11.]
	The employees at Robinson were not helpful when I was shopping.	SQ4	[11.]
Satisfaction	Overall, I am happy with the service at Robinson.	SA1	[5.]
	Overall, I am satisfied with the service at Robinson.	SA2	[5.]
	The service provided by Robinson’s employees does not meet my expectations.	SA3	[11.]
Value	Considering the price paid and the benefits received, the value of the service provided by Robinson is good.	VA1	[5.]
	I feel that the value of the service provided by Robinson is good.	VA2	[5.]
Trust	I feel that I cannot fully trust Robinson.	TR1	[5.]
	I feel that the employees at Robinson can be relied upon to assist me when I need help.	TR2	[5.]
Commitment	I feel emotionally attached to Robinson.	CO1	[5.]
	I have a sense of loyalty towards Robinson.	CO2	[5.]
	Robinson has a deep personal meaning for me.	CO3	[5.]
Pricing Problem	I pay a fair price at Robinson.	PP1	[5.]
	The price of products at Robinson is relatively cheap.	PP2	[5.]
Alternative Attractiveness	Overall, shopping at competing retailers would be much more beneficial than at Robinson.	AA1	[5.]
	I feel more interested in other retailers, not Robinson.	AA2	[11.]
	Other retailers offer newer and more diverse products.	AA3	[11.]
	Other retailers offer better prices than Robinson.	AA4	[13.]
Attitude Toward Switching	Switching from Robinson to another retailer in the near future would be a bad idea.	AS1	[5.]
	Switching from Robinson to another retailer in the near future would be	AS2	[5.]

Variables	Indicators	Code	Source
	pointless.		
	Switching from Robinson in the near future would be beneficial.	AS3	[5.]
	Switching from Robinson in the near future would be a wise decision.	AS4	[5.]
	I would be happy to switch from Robinson to another retailer.	AS5	[5.]
	I have always enjoyed shopping at different fashion stores.	PB1	[5.]
Past Behavior	In shopping for fashion products, I have not only shopped at a single retailer in the past few months.	PB2	[5.]
	Alternative Seeking	I prefer sticking with the fashion retailer I usually visit rather than trying other service providers that I am unsure of.	VS1
I am very cautious about trying different fashion retailers.		VS2	[5.]
If I already like the existing service, I rarely switch just to try other fashion retailers.		VS3	[5.]
Switching Intention	I will definitely switch from Robinson in the near future.	SI1	[5.]
	There is a possibility that I will switch from Robinson in the near future.	SI2	[5.]
	I intend to switch from Robinson in the near future.	SI3	[5.]

The primary data gathered through the distribution of questionnaires to Robinson customers in Semarang city, Indonesia. The questionnaire was divided into two parts, the participants' demographic information and questions about PPM factors. The minimum required number of participants for the study was 160, and a total of 234 data were collected. However, 28 questionnaires were excluded as they did not pass the screening criteria, where participants indicated that they had never made at least two purchases at Robinson. Therefore, the usable questionnaire data amounted to 209 participants.

Hypothesis testing and model evaluation were conducted using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) method. According to [14.], SEM is a statistical model capable of elucidating intricate relationships among variables. This approach enables the simultaneous examination of a network of interconnected relationships,

including those between dependent and independent variables. To address unresolved issues that conventional analysis methods cannot tackle, the SEM analysis was conducted utilizing the AMOS software.

IV. RESULTS

A. Path Diagram

The path diagram is a graphical representation of a structural model. Within the structural model, there are indicators that represent latent constructs, both exogenous and endogenous variables. From the existing path diagram, a system of equations can be derived that describes the composition of each indicator from its corresponding latent constructs. The path diagram in this study consists of push factors, pull factors, mooring factors, and switching intention, as shown in full model of path diagram in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Full model path diagram of PPM factors and switching intention

B. Model Identification

In Structural Equation Modeling, there are three possibilities that can occur with a model. An unidentified model (if $t \geq s / 2$ or negative degrees of freedom), a just identified model (if $t = s / 2$ or degrees of freedom = 0), and an overidentified model (if $t \leq s / 2$ or positive degrees of freedom). In SEM, the aim is to obtain an overidentified model and avoid underidentified models. From the processing using AMOS software, the calculation of degrees of freedom is obtained as follows:

Number of distinct sample moments = 378
 Number of distinct parameters to be estimated = 60
 Degrees of freedom (378 - 60) = 318

From the results, it can be seen that the number of estimated variables is 60. The symbol s denotes the count of variances and covariances among observable variables, calculated using the formula $(p+q)(p+q+1)$, where p represents the number of indicators for the endogenous latent variables and q represents the number of indicators for

the exogenous latent variables. As the number of estimated parameters (t) is less than the number of variances and covariances among observable variables, or in other words, when the degrees of freedom possess a positive value, the model is considered overidentified.

C. Model Specification

The data processing results of the structural model show a path diagram between endogenous latent variables consisting of error values, estimates, and mathematical equations in the structural model. The exogenous variables in this study are push factors, pull factors, and mooring factors. The endogenous latent variable is switching intention. It is important to note the loading factors of each indicator in the measurement model. If the loading factor of an indicator is less than 0.5, it is considered inappropriate and will be excluded from the model. The measurement results of the exogenous variables, including push, pull, and mooring, using AMOS software can be seen in Fig. 3. Moreover, the measurement of endogenous variable (switching intention) figured in Fig. 4.

Fig. 3: Exogenous variables measurement

Fig. 4: Endogenous variable measurement

D. Model Respecification

The model was then respecified to improve the fit of the model to the data, based on the results of the previous goodness-of-fit tests. The respecification of the model was conducted when there were offering estimates, overall model fit validity, and model reliability that were not satisfactory.

From the CFA model for the exogenous variables it was known that the model still required an improvement, as some indicators had loading factors less than 0.5 and the goodness-of-fit test for the model was still unsatisfactory. Therefore, a respecification was performed as resulted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Final model

E. Goodness of Fit Test

Next, the goodness-of-fit testing of the final model was conducted to assess the fit of all variables in the tested

model. Table 2 shows the test result and can be explained as a good model.

Table 2: Model Goodness of Fit Test Result

GOF	Criteria	Result	Decision
Chi-Square	The lower the better	498.020	Good Fit
χ^2/df	$1 \leq \chi^2/df \leq 3$ good fit	2,721	Good Fit
NCP	The lower the better	315,020	Good Fit
GFI	$GFI \geq 0,90$ good fit $0,80 \leq GFI \leq 0,90$ marginal fit	0,811	Marginal Fit
RMSEA	$RMSEA \leq 0,05$ good fit	0,091	Good Fit
ECVI	Small value and close with ECVI saturated = 0,68	2,86	Good Fit
NFI	$NFI \geq 0,90$ good fit $0,80 \leq NFI \leq 0,90$ marginal fit	0,856	Marginal Fit
AGFI	$AGFI \geq 0,90$ good fit $0,80 \leq AGFI \leq 0,90$ marginal fit	0,761	Bad Fit
RFI	$RFI \geq 0,90$ good fit $0,80 \leq RFI \leq 0,90$ marginal fit	0,835	Marginal Fit
IFI	$IFI \geq 0,90$ good fit $0,80 \leq IFI \leq 0,90$ marginal fit	0,904	Good Fit
CFI	$CFI \geq 0,90$ good fit	0,903	Good Fit
PGFI	The higher the better	0,642	Good Fit

F. Hypothesis Test

Finally, hypothesis testing was conducted to determine whether there was a significant effect of the push, pull, and mooring variables on customer’s switching intention. Hypothesis testing was performed by examining the CR values and comparing them with the critical *t*-value and

significance value < 0.005. The critical *t*-value based on the *t*-distribution table with degrees of freedom $df = n - k = 208 - 4 = 204$ and a significance level $\alpha = 5\%$, so that the *t*-critical = 1.976. The results of the hypothesis testing can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3: Hypothesis Test Result

	Hypothesis	t-value	Result	Decision
H1	Push factors on switching intention	-0.518	H ₀ rejected	No significant effect
H2	Pull factors on switching intention	2.090	Do not reject H ₀	Significant effect exists
H3	Mooring factors on switching intention	2.813	Do not reject H ₀	Significant effect exists
H4	Mooring factors on the relationship between push factors and switching intention	1.182	H ₀ rejected	No significant effect
H5	Mooring factors on the relationship between pull factors and switching intention	2.568	Do not reject H ₀	Significant effect exists

V. DISCUSSION

A. Hypothesis 1: The effect of push factors on switching intention

In the variable of push factors, there were initially thirteen indicators used in the model. These thirteen indicators are divided into several groups related to quality, satisfaction, value, commitment, and price perception. Based on the calculation of the standardized regression loading factor, it was found that eight indicators had values below 0.5. These indicators are PP2 (0.458), SA3 (0.403), SQ4 (0.353), and SQ3 (0.321). If the standardized regression values or loading factors are below 0.5, it means that those question indicators are not sufficiently significant and can be eliminated from the model.

In the similar loading factors calculation, it was also found that the most significant indicator or the one with the largest influence on push factors is SA1 (Overall, I am satisfied with Robinson's service). This indicator measures the level of customer satisfaction with Robinson's service overall. This means that the higher the significance, the lower the customer satisfaction. It implies that the most influential push factor is low satisfaction. The second most influential indicator is SA2 (Overall, I am happy with the service at Robinson). This indicator is still part of satisfaction, indicating that low satisfaction with Robinson's service has the most influence on customers' intention to switch. This is inline with the study by [15.], which shows that satisfaction has a significant influence on customer switching intention. Customer satisfaction is an essential part of marketing concepts and significantly affects a company's success.

In the context of the PPM Model, push factors are depicted as negative factors that subsequently drive consumers to switch from their initial service provider. In this study, push factors are measured by indicators or assessments of quality, satisfaction, value, trust, commitment, and price perception at Robinson's retail. However, in the final overall model, some indicators were considered insignificant.

After conducting hypothesis testing based on the output from the AMOS software, a t -value of -0.518 ($df = 204$; $p = 0.605$) was obtained. This indicates that hypothesis 1 is rejected, suggesting that push factors do not have a significant influence on switching intention or customers' intention to switch. This result indicates that customers' intention to switch from Robinson's retail is not driven by low levels of service, satisfaction, value, and commitment. Thus, push factors such as low quality, low satisfaction, low

value, low commitment, and high price perception are not significantly influential in influencing customers to switch from Robinson's retail. These findings differ from a previous study by [5.], where push factors had a positive influence on customers' willingness to switch. The difference in findings could be attributed to the characteristics of respondents in this study, who may not prioritize low quality, low satisfaction, low value, and low trust, as well as high price perception when shopping for fashion. Additionally, other dominant factors may have a greater influence on the desire to switch, such as pull factors. [5.] stated that although push factors have a positive influence on the intention to switch, they are usually not significant and have a small impact compared to mooring and pull factors. Therefore, [5.] further stated that the variables that serve as push factors are not the main focus in studies related to the intention to switch.

B. Hypothesis 2: The effect of pull factors on switching intention

The pull factors variable consisted of four indicators in the initial model. All those indicators had loading factors above 0.5, indicating their significance, and all of them were considered suitable to be included in the final model.

The indicator with the highest loading factor or considered the most significant was AA3 (Other retailers offer newer and more diverse products). This means that the most influential factor in attracting customers is the availability of newer and more diverse products from other retailers, which attracts customers to switch to other retailers. The next significant indicator is AA2 (I feel interested in other retailers, not Robinson).

In a previous study by [6.], attractive factors such as the availability of more enjoyable and affordable products offered by other service providers had the most significant influence in attracting customers to switch. Similarly, in [15.] study on food retailers, the availability of a greater variety of products in other retailers was the most influential factor for the respondents.

Based on the output from the AMOS software, a t -value of 2.090 ($df = 204$, $p = 0.037$) was obtained. This indicates that hypothesis 2 is not rejected, and it can be concluded that pull factors have a positive influence on customers' intention to switch from Robinson's retail. This suggests that customers want to switch because of the alternative attractiveness offered by other retailers, such as a wider variety of products, which attracts customers to switch from Robinson.

Furthermore, it was also found that pull or attracting factors have a high level of influence on the intention to switch after mooring factors. This is consistent with previous studies by [5.], [11.], and [13.]. This situation indicates that in the decision-making process, consumers tend to consider factors related to competitor products. Therefore, the more customers are familiar with competitor products, the easier it is for them to switch from their current service provider.

Research [5.] also stated that the attribute characteristics of alternative service products would cause customers to reevaluate the original product. The evaluation of alternative attractiveness includes factors related to how competitor service products satisfy customers, provide greater value or benefits to customers, and build customer trust.

C. Hypothesis 3: The effect of mooring factors on switching intention

The mooring factors variable included in the model consisted of seven indicators divided into two sub-variables: attitude towards switching and past behavior. Based on the calculation of loading factors, it was found that two indicators had loading factors below 0.5, indicating their insignificance, and they were subsequently removed from the model, i.e. AS1 and AS2.

In the same calculation, it was also found that the indicator with the greatest influence on mooring factors was PB1 (I have frequently changed fashion shopping locations in the past) with an estimated loading factor of 0.912. The next influential indicator was AS5 (I would be happy to switch from Robinson to another retailer).

Mooring factors in this study were measured based on customer attitudes towards change, past behavior, and the desire for variety. However, only attitudes towards change and past behavior served as indicators in the model.

From the data analysis, a t -value of 2.813 ($df = 204$, $p = 0.005$) was obtained. This indicates that hypothesis 3 is not rejected, and it can be concluded that mooring factors have a positive influence on switching intention or customers' intention to switch. Furthermore, it was also found that mooring factors had the highest t -value among the other PPM factors, meaning that mooring factors had the greatest influence on customers' switching intention. Compared to the other two factors, mooring factors are more related to an individual's personal perspective rather than the influence of the current or alternative service providers.

These results are consistent with a previous study by [5.], where it was found that mooring factors had the most significant influence on customers' intention to switch. Consumers tend to choose to switch from one service provider to a new one if they have a history of switching service providers, hold a positive attitude towards switching, and enjoy seeking variety. Some variables proposed by [5.] for mooring factors were not used in this study because they were considered inappropriate, and another variable, the enjoyment of seeking alternatives, could not be included in

the model, possibly due to differences in the research subject.

D. Hypothesis 4: The effect of mooring factors on the relationship between push factors and switching intention

The moderation effect suggests that mooring factors can moderate or influence the impact of push factors on customers' switching intentions. This means that the presence or strength of mooring factors can either amplify or attenuate the relationship between push factors and switching intention. For instance, if mooring factors are strong, customers may be more resistant to switching, even in the presence of significant push factors. Strong mooring factors can create a sense of loyalty or attachment to the current service provider, making customers less likely to consider alternatives. On the other hand, weak mooring factors may enhance the impact of push factors, making customers more susceptible to switching when faced with dissatisfaction or negative experiences.

Based on the output from the AMOS software, which modeled the interaction and moderation relationship between push factors and mooring factors, a t -value of 1.182 ($df = 204$; $p = 0.237$) was obtained. Therefore, it can be concluded that the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that mooring factors did not moderate the relationship between push factors and the intention to switch, meaning that there was no influence of mooring factors on the impact of push factors on the intention to switch, whether the mooring factors were strong or weak.

E. Hypothesis 5: The effect of mooring factors on the relationship between pull factors and switching intention

The effect of mooring factors as moderators suggests that the presence or strength of mooring factors can either amplify or attenuate the impact of pull factors on customers' switching intentions. If mooring factors are strong, customers may be less likely to be influenced by the attractiveness of pull factors and remain loyal to their current service provider. Strong mooring factors can create a sense of attachment or loyalty, making customers resistant to switching even in the presence of appealing alternatives. On the other hand, weak mooring factors may enhance the impact of pull factors, making customers more inclined to consider switching when presented with attractive offerings from alternative providers.

Based on the output from the AMOS software, which modeled the interaction and moderation relationship between pull factors and mooring factors, a t -value of 2.568 ($df = 204$; $p = 0.005$) was obtained. Since the null hypothesis was failed to be rejected, this result indicated that mooring factors significantly moderate the relationship between pull factors and switching intention. The findings suggest that mooring factors play a crucial role in determining the impact of pull factors on customers' intention to switch. [5.] states that if mooring factors are weak, customers are more likely to consider switching when pull factors are strong compared to when push factors are weak. However, if mooring factors are strong, there is no difference in switching intention regardless of whether the pull factors are strong or weak.

This implies that customers who are strongly attached to a service provider due to mooring factors are less likely to switch to another provider, even if the alternative provider offers significant attractiveness.

The implications of this study suggest that customers will remain loyal to Robinson and not switch if their mooring factors are strong. Based on the research by Bansal et al. (2005), when customers are bound to a service provider due to mooring factors, they are unlikely to switch to an alternative provider, despite having an interest in the alternatives. In this case, it means that if customers feel attached to Robinson due to mooring factors such as lack of interest in trying other retailers or a closed attitude towards switching, they will continue to stay with Robinson even if other retailers offer more advantageous factors such as lower prices, promotions, and diverse products.

F. Further Implication and Recommendation

Based on the hypotheses formulated in the study, it can be concluded that the intention to switch among Robinson customers is influenced by several factors. These factors include internal factors from the service provider itself, in this case, Robinson, such as push factors like low quality leading to low customer satisfaction, low value, high perceived prices, and low customer commitment to Robinson. However, based on the testing, it was found that these factors are not significant. On the contrary, external factors such as the attractiveness of competitors and personal factors such as customers' attitudes towards switching and past behavior have a greater impact on customers' intention to switch.

The results of this study slightly differ from previous research by [5.], which found a significant influence of all three factors (push, pull, and mooring) on customer switching intention. This difference can be attributed to variations in the objects being studied, where the offered products differ, resulting in different responses as well. Although the findings indicate that push factors are not considered significant in influencing customer switching intention in this study, service providers should still strive to improve quality and enhance customer satisfaction. The implication of these findings is that the more customers are aware of alternative service providers, the lower their tolerance for low quality and satisfaction, making it easier for them to switch if they find another provider offering greater benefits. Furthermore, the fashion industry is a large and continuously evolving industry, providing customers with a wide range of choices. The abundance of fashion retail service providers makes it very convenient for consumers to switch. This is also supported by the fact that the majority of consumers tend not to feel attached or loyal to a single service provider, as indicated by questionnaire data showing that most of the respondents reported shopping at multiple fashion retailers. If continuous improvement and keeping up with developments are not pursued, there is a possibility of a continued decline in transactions at Robinson.

The main focus of push factors was on quality, customer satisfaction, value, commitment, and price perception. In this regard, Robinson could start by improving the quality of both its products and services. According to [17.], a product is a good or service produced to be used by consumers to meet their needs and provide satisfaction. The products offered by Robinson are retail services that provide various fashion items such as clothing, shoes, and bags. From the data obtained through the questionnaire, it was found that the majority of respondents gave neutral and positive answers regarding the quality of Robinson's products. A small percentage, around 10% of the respondents, considered Robinson's products to be poor or below average. Based on these responses, it can be inferred that Robinson's product quality can be described as mediocre or average. This is also related to the pull factors, where if the product quality is average and supported by strong attractive factors from competitors, customers will be more inclined to switch. Therefore, one strategy that Robinson can adopt is to improve the quality of its products and services, so that customers will remain interested in shopping at Robinson. In addition to improving quality, diversifying products and keeping up with fashion trends can also be done to make Robinson the primary destination for customers seeking new fashion trends. Furthermore, Robinson can enhance the quality of its service by providing training to employees to improve their friendliness and politeness in the long term, making them more helpful to confused buyers in need of assistance during shopping, thus making customers more comfortable.

Another factor is related to price. One approach is to offer discounts, especially during specific events, to keep customers interested in repeat shopping at Robinson compared to competing retailers, while considering the company's costs and benefits. Regarding customer satisfaction, [6.] stated that satisfaction is closely related to factors such as quality, price, and value. The closer the comparison between the quality and benefits received and the price paid, the higher the level of customer satisfaction, which influences their intention to switch. Therefore, if the quality, value, and price are aligned, customer satisfaction will increase, leading to repeat transactions.

Moreover, it is known that pull factors have a significant influence on customer switching decisions. Customers are most interested in switching when they are attracted to alternative options. According to [18.], consumer product knowledge significantly affects information search, where strong product knowledge encourages consumers to learn and assimilate new information more easily. In relation to this, Robinson can also do the same by actively conducting research on the market and its major competitors. By understanding the market well, current fashion trends, customer preferences, as well as getting to know competitors, their strategies, and products, Robinson can emulate the strategies used by competitors, as well as the fashion trends offered by competitors, so that customers perceive that Robinson also offers similar products at better prices.

Lastly, because mooring factors are more related to the personal preferences of the customers themselves, what Robinson can do is to improve the quality of service and customer satisfaction to reduce the desire to switch. The research shows that customers have a positive attitude towards switching. It is also known that mooring factors have a significant influence on the relationship between pull factors and switching intention, which means that even if competing retailers have attractive features that make customers want to switch, if the mooring factors are strong, customers will not switch. In relation to this, Robinson should engage in active promotions emphasizing the advantages and strengths of the products offered, as well as the available promotions. This can influence the personal perspective of customers regarding their desire to switch, and it is expected to attract new customers who have not previously shopped at Robinson. Additionally, keeping up with the rapid technological advancements, it would be beneficial for Robinson to establish a practical and popular online store that caters to the preferences of current customers.

VI. CONCLUSION

Several push factors that influenced customers' switching intentions from Robinson to other retailers were low quality, low satisfaction, low value, low commitment, and high price perception. Based on the research findings, it was revealed that push factors themselves did not have a significant influence on customers' decision to switch. Pull factors, on the other hand, consisted of alternative attractiveness, which refers to the attractiveness of competitors that entices customers to switch. According to the research results, pull factors had a significant influence on customers' switching intentions. Pull factors were the second most influential factors in customers' decision to switch. Mooring factors, which influenced customers' switching intentions, consisted of attitude toward switching and past behavior. The research findings showed that mooring factors had a significant influence on customers' switching intentions and had the greatest impact. Mooring factors also moderated the relationship between pull factors and switching intentions significantly. If mooring factors were strong, customers would not switch from Robinson even if alternative attractiveness was strong. On the other hand, mooring factors did not moderate the relationship between push factors and switching intentions significantly. It implies that there would be no difference in customers' switching intentions due to the influence of mooring factors. If mooring factors significantly moderated the relationship between push factors and switching intentions, weak mooring factors would make customers highly likely to switch when push factors were high compared to when push factors were weak.

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